

CASTOR OIL BASED BIO-URETHANE NANOCOMPOSITES

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1 Introduction

Renewable resource polymers have recently garnered a great deal of attention due to the anticipated petroleum shortage and growing environmental concerns [1]. The most widely used renewable raw materials include polysaccharides, wood, proteins, and plant oils [2]. Among them, vegetable oils are the most widely used renewable resources due to their low toxicity, inherent biodegradability, ready availability, and relatively low price [3]. Vegetable oils such as corn, soybean, sunflower, linseed and castor oil constitute one major class of renewable resources. The main composition of these oils is saturated and unsaturated fatty acids. They can be polymerized to form an elastomer and promise alternative material resources to petrochemical derived resin.

Castor oil is a versatile vegetable oil due to its unique composition in which the main component is the 12-hydroxy-9-cis-octadecenoic acid containing one double bond and one hydroxyl group. The rich chemistry of raw castor oil is attributed to its structure, which makes it a good starting material for a wide range of applications [4].

Polyurethane (PU) a diverse family of materials with widespread application in a number of technological areas and a range of commodity products, such as polymers for adhesives, automotive parts, footwear, furnishings, construction, and in paints and coatings for appliances [5-9]. They can be easily prepared by simple polyaddition reaction of diols, isocyanates and chain extenders [7]. The reaction advances with the nucleophilic attack on the carbon atom of the isocyanate group by a nucleophilic group (OH, NH₂) present in various compounds such as alcohols and amines. Reaction with an alcohol results in the formation of a urethane group (-NH-CO-O-). In the case of amines, urea (-NH-CO-NH-) bonds are formed and poly(urea-urethanes) are obtained [5, 6].

In addition, the isocyanates react with epoxy resin via the epoxy group to produce an oxazolidone structure or with a hydroxyl group to yield a urethane linkage.

The objective of this study was to prepare bio-urethane (BIO-U) composites using epoxidized/methoxylated castor oil, and addition of surface modified Talc and multi-walled nanotube (MWNT). The main problem for the composite properties is the achievement of a good filler distribution in the polymer matrix. The particle distribution in the polymer matrix depends mostly on interactions between matrix and filler. The addition of surface-modified filler can influence the improvement of the properties through better dispersion of the filler in the matrix and through the modification of interactions at the interface. The morphology, thermal and mechanical properties of the resulting nanocomposites were investigated.

2 Experimental

2.1 Materials

Castor oil was extracted from the seeds of Castor plant. Tin (II) 2-ethylhexanoate, 3-(triethoxysilyl) propyl isocyanate (TEPI), poly (tetramethylene ether) glycol (PTMG, Mw ≈ 2000), and 1,4-phenylene diisocyanate (PDI) were supplied by Sigma-Aldrich. Talc was provided by Youngwoo Mires (S-A400, median size = 11 μm, Chungju city, Chungbuk, Korea). MWNT (CM-95, purity = 95 wt %, average diameter = 15 nm, average length = 20 μm, specific gravity = 1.8, Iljin Nanotech Co., Ltd., Seoul, Korea) was used as received. Talc and MWNT were predried in a convection oven for at least 12 h at 50 °C to remove any moisture. Other chemical compounds were reagent grade and were used as received.

2.2 Instrumentation

Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectra of samples were measured with a PerkinElmer infrared spectrometer (Spectrum 2000, Shelton, CT) in the wavenumber range from 400 to 4000 cm^{-1} .

Proton Nuclear Magnetic Resonance ($^1\text{H-NMR}$) spectra recorded at room temperature on a Bruker AC-250 FT-NMR spectrometer. Ten milligrams of the sample was dissolved in 0.5 ml of CDCl_3 and was subjected to the $^1\text{H-NMR}$ measurements.

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) observations of the samples were performed on a Hitachi S-4300 model (Tokyo, Japan).

Thermal properties of the nanocomposite samples were determined by a Perkin Elmer Jade differential scanning calorimetry (DSC, Shelton, CT). Thermal history of the samples was removed by scanning from -20 to 200 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ with the heating rate of 20 $^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$. After cooling down the specimen at the rate of -20 $^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$ to room temperature, it was reheated at -20 to 200 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ with the heating rate of 20 $^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$ and the DSC curves were obtained.

Thermal stability of the samples was determined by thermogravimetry (TG, PerkinElmer TGS-2). The TG curves were obtained under an N_2 atmosphere and scanned from 20 to 800 $^{\circ}\text{C}$.

2.3 Epoxidation of castor oil

Hydrogen peroxide (12 g) was gradually charged into a mixture of castor oil (50 g) and formic acid (12 g) during the first 5 h of reaction at 50 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. The mixture was stirred for a further 5 h and then diluted with water and ethyl acetate. The aqueous phase was removed using a separatory funnel and the residue was evaporated on a rotary evaporator.

2.4 Synthesis of methoxylated castor oil

Epoxidized castor oil (10 g) was added with stirring over a period of 10 min to a mixture of methanol (10 ml), water (1 g), isopropanol (30 ml), and fluoboric acid (0.4 g) maintained at 40 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. The mixture was stirred at about 50 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 1 h, at which stage aqueous ammonia (0.6 ml) was added to quench the reaction. The reaction mixture is then concentrated in a rotary evaporator, which was followed by high vacuum.

2.5 Preparation of PU prepolymer

PDI (8 g), PTMG (45 g), tin (II) 2-ethylhexanoate (0.05 ml) and toluene (50 g) were added into the

reactor equipped with a reflux condenser, nitrogen gas inlet, and mechanical stirrer. The reaction mixture was then continuously stirred with a speed of 80 rpm for 2 h at 60 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ to yield a light yellow, low viscosity liquid.

2.6 Surface modification of Talc

Stearic acid (SA, 10 g) was dissolved in ethyl acetate (EA, 50 ml), and then 3-(triethoxysilyl) propyl isocyanate (TEPI, 7.5 g) and Tin (II) 2-ethylhexanoate (0.05 ml) were added with stirring to a solution maintained at 40 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. The solution was stirred at 40 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 1 h. Talc (20g) was added to the above-mentioned solution and the mixture was dispersed for 2 h in an ultrasonic bath at 50 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. The SA modified Talc (Talc-SA) were filtered, washed with EA and dried in the oven at 80 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 24 h.

2.7 In-situ polymerization of BIO-U

The prepolymer (20 g) was pre-mixed with methoxylated castor oil (or epoxidized castor oil, 2 g) and then tin (II) 2-ethylhexanoate (0.05 ml) was added. The resulting composition was poured into a glass Petri dish and cured at 60 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 2 h.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Synthesis of methoxylated castor oil

Fig. 1 demonstrates $^1\text{H-NMR}$ spectra of the epoxidized castor oil and methoxylated castor oil. The $^1\text{H-NMR}$ spectrum of castor oil presented double bond protons at 5.3-5.6 ppm (Fig. 1a). In the $^1\text{H-NMR}$ spectrum of epoxidized castor oil, the small peak at 2.8-3.2 ppm indicates epoxy ring formation. The peaks at 2.1 ppm result from the protons on the $-\text{CH}_2$ groups adjacent to the methyl ester (Fig. 1c). The major differences between the ^1H NMR spectrum of castor oil and the resulting methoxylated castor oil are the disappearance of the epoxy ring protons at 2.8-3.2 ppm and the appearance of methyl ester protons at 3.7 ppm. The epoxidized- and methoxylated castor oil were further characterized by FTIR spectroscopy (Fig. 2). For castor oil (Fig. 2a) the characteristic peaks at 3008, 1650 and 721 cm^{-1} are attributed to the stretching vibration of $=\text{C-H}$, $-\text{C}=\text{C}-$ and $-\text{CH}=\text{CH}-$, respectively. After epoxidation reaction, the almost complete disappearance of double bonds band at

3008 cm^{-1} at 50 °C after 10 h was observed. Also the presence of new peaks in the FTIR spectrum of Fig. 2b at 831 cm^{-1} , attributed to the epoxy group, confirmed the success of the epoxidation reaction of castor oil. The FTIR spectrum of the methoxylated castor oil is presented in Fig. 2c. In comparison with the spectrum of epoxidized castor oil, the disappearance of epoxy groups and the emergence of the hydroxy groups (at 3470 cm^{-1}) were obvious. The peak at the 3470 cm^{-1} was derived from the epoxy group via ring opening reaction.

3.2 Surface modification of Talc and MWNT

Fig. 3 shows the FTIR spectra of the Talc and Talc-SA. The -OH stretching band of the octahedral Mg-O-H unit in Talc occurs at 3677 cm^{-1} . The -SiO vibration occurs in the 1017 cm^{-1} region. The libration modes of the Mg-O-H in end-member Talc are observed in bands at 670 and 464 cm^{-1} , respectively. Compared with without the TEPI-SA entity Talc, the absorptions at 2855-2955 cm^{-1} (-CH₂) and 1750 cm^{-1} (-NHCO) for Talc-SA were ascribed to the TEPI-SA groups, indicating that the SA groups had successfully introduced into the Talc.

The MWNT were electron beam (EB)-irradiated in air at room temperature with an EB accelerator (ELV 4, EB Tech Co., Ltd., Daejeon, Korea). Irradiation doses of 1200 kGy were used [10]. Fig. 4 demonstrates the FTIR spectra of the pristine MWNT and MWNT1200. As depicted in Fig. 4a, the strong bands at 2920 and 2852 cm^{-1} on the curve are well known, due to asymmetrical and symmetrical stretching of -CH₂, respectively. The band at 2958 cm^{-1} is assigned to the asymmetrical stretching of -CH₃. The peak at 1635 cm^{-1} can be associated with the stretching of the MWNT backbone. FTIR spectra of MWNT after EB irradiation at 1200 kGy (Fig. 4b) showed new peaks at 1782-1720 cm^{-1} due to the -C=O bond resulting from the stretch mode of carboxylic groups.

SEM image in Fig. 5 give a clear picture of the morphological changes of the Talc surface after SA treatment. It is clear that modified particles have a rough surface topography. Similarly, after 1200 kGy irradiation, the smooth surface of pristine MWNT was disappeared, many wrinkled structure were formed, and the surface roughness increased (Fig. 6). In general, the surface of the synthesized CNT is smooth and relatively defects free. However, stresses can induce Stone Wales transformations,

resulting in the formation of heptagons and concave areas of deformation on the nanotubes [11]. As a result the effective surface area available for contact with the matrix increases.

3.3 Morphology of BIO-U nanocomposites

The in-situ polymerization of BIO-U in the presence of the Talc-SA or MWNT1200 was performed with the same monomer ratios as described above. The required amount of surface modified nanofiller was dispersed in the prepolymer at room temperature by mechanical premixing and bath sonication for 2 h. The prepolymer was pre-mixed with modified castor oil and then tin (II) 2-ethylhexanoate was added. The yield of the in situ polymerization of BIO-U (> 99 %) was unaffected by the addition of Talc-SA and MWNT1200.

The FTIR spectra (Fig. 7) of the synthesized BIO-U indicated the absence of any residual isocyanate (no absorption at 2270 cm^{-1}) and showed strong absorptions at 1730 and 3330 cm^{-1} indicating the formation of the urethane linkage. The FTIR spectra of the BIO-U exhibited the typical bands for PU; -NH, at 3300-3400 cm^{-1} , -CH₂ at 2850-2970 cm^{-1} , -C=O in bonded urethane group at 1680-1720 cm^{-1} and -C-O-C- in ester group at 1053 cm^{-1} [12].

Almost all the infrared studies on PU were focused on two principal vibration regions: the -NH stretching vibration (3200-3400 cm^{-1}) and the carbonyl -C=O stretching vibration in the amide I region (1680-1720 cm^{-1}). PU elastomers are capable of forming several kinds of hydrogen bonds due to the presence of a donor -NH group and a -C=O acceptor group in the urethane linkage. This is due to hard segment-hard segment or hard segment-soft segment hydrogen bonding can exist [12]. As show in Fig. 8, two absorption bands are observed in carbonyl region, which should reflect the properties of hydrogen bonding in the synthesized BIO-U. In order of increasing wave-numbers two carbonyl stretching bands of BIO-U are observed, these are hydrogen-bonded carbonyls formed between adjacent hard segments (-C=O_{HB-HS}, 1696 cm^{-1}) and hydrogen-bonded carbonyls with ether oxygen of soft segments via the -NH group (-C=O_{HB-SS}, ~1730 cm^{-1}). The PU-PTMG shows two carbonyl peaks at near 1730 and 1696 cm^{-1} due to the -C=O_{HB-SS} and the -C=O_{HB-HS}, respectively. As compared with the PU-PTMG, the addition of 20 wt% of castor oil, epoxidized castor oil and methoxylated castor oil

leads to a decrease in the $\text{-C=O}_{\text{HB-HS}}$ band accompany with an increase in $\text{-C=O}_{\text{HB-SS}}$ band. These results suggest that phase mixing of PU matrix is enhanced addition of castor oil and methoxylated castor oil because of decreasing fraction of hard segment-hard segment hydrogen bonding ($\text{-NH}\cdots\text{O=C-}$) in hard segment domains and increasing fraction of hard segment-soft segment hydrogen bonding ($\text{-NH}\cdots\text{O-}$) in the phase mixing. Thus, the decrease in hard domain size and therefore the extent of interurethane interactions in phase mixing morphologies are expected. In the case of ECO-U, the appearance of a single -NH band at 3330 cm^{-1} which is growing bigger with the nature of cross-linking of the hard segment suggested that most of its -NH groups were hydrogen bonded [12]. Dispersion of the nanofiller in polymer matrix is one of the most important factors that crucially influence on the properties of the nanocomposites. The dispersion of surface-modified Talc and MWNT in BIO-U matrix was analyzed using SEM. The fracture surfaces of BIO-U and nanocomposites containing 2 wt% of Talc-SA and MWNT1200 are presented in Fig. 9, Fig. 10 and Fig. 11 respectively. The samples were prepared by breaking the liquid N_2 frozen film specimens and a thin platinum coating was applied to improve the conductivity for good image observation.

SEM micrograph of the CTO-U, ECO-U and MCO-U (Fig. 9) show a surface like beach lines, originated when sample was cutted and characteristic of highly amorphous or elastomeric material which has process memory to cut [13]. Moreover it is difficult to correctly identify the presence of hard- and soft-segments, though the layers are uniformly distributed. These results agree well with the FTIR analysis.

By comparison of micrographs of CTO-U composite film with 2 wt% of Talc and Talc-SA, differences in the morphology of the fracture area were noticed. So-called nodules, regarded as bundles of parallel oriented macromolecules, and voids that were formed during fracturing. The abbreviation of the sample code CTO-U/Talc-SA-2wt%, for example, means that the content of Talc-SA in the CTO-U was 2 wt% and Talc was treated with SA. At the fracture area of the CTO-U/Talc-2wt% nanocomposite, the highest number of nodules and voids can be easily identified (Fig. 10a). However CTO-

U/Talc-SA-2wt% had good interfacial adhesion between matrix and Talc-SA layers (Fig. 10b). The other nanocomposites were almost the same morphology as the CTO-U/Talc-SA-2wt% one.

Fig. 11 shows SEM images of the fracture surface of MTO-U/MWNT-2wt% and MCO-U/MWNT1200-2wt% nanocomposites. For MCO-U/MWNT1200-2wt% (Fig.11b), we found that the MWNTs dispersed well in the polymer matrix. Most of the MWNTs were broken in the interface rather than pulled out from the polymer matrix. In contrast the MCO/MWNT-2wt% nanocomposite showed a different morphology (Fig. 11a). Most of the MWNT fibers were pulled out from the MCO-U matrix. Additionally, it is visible that some of the nanofiller aggregates dewetted from the matrix.

According to these observations, it seems that in the MCO-U/MWNT-2wt% failures occurs through both the mechanisms of dewetting and shear yielding of the polymer matrix. In case of MCO/MWNT1200-2wt% nanocomposite, the topology at the fracture area is rougher. It seems that in this system the most pronounced fracture mechanism is shear yielding. Such a discrepancy demonstrated that a stronger interfacial adhesion existed between the MCO-U matrix and MWNT1200. The morphology of MCO-U/MWNT and CTO-U/MWNT composites system exhibited almost no change relative to MCO-U/MWNT system.

3.4 DSC thermal properties

Fig. 12 shows the first- and second-scan DSC thermograms of the synthesized CTO-U, ECO-U, MCO-U and PU-PTMG. The first-scan DSC thermogram of PU-PTMG exhibited bimodal melting peaks at 13.3 and $106.7\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. The higher- and lower-melting peaks were attributed to crystallized hard- and soft-segment crystals, respectively during the curing step at $60\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. For ECO-U, one can see the obvious endothermic peak of the melting of soft segment at $21.7\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. However, no clear peaks were observed for the other samples. These results clearly suggest that incorporation of the castor oil and epoxidized castor oil into the polymer glycols are quite effective on the crystallizability of soft-segment in the BIO-U. In addition, the crystallization temperature (T_c) of all samples was undetectable by the DSC within the test temperature range. This indicated that crystallization of hard- and

soft-segments of CTO-U, ECO-U and MCO-U is strongly inhibited due to the high degree of phase mixing as shown in Fig. 8.

In the second-scan thermogram which was obtained via reheating at 20 °C/min after cooling from 200 to -20 °C at a rate of -20 °C/min, the lower-melting peak of CTO-U and MCO-U appeared because crystallization was accomplished fully enough regardless of the fast cooling. In case of ECO-U, the lower-temperature peak was shift to a higher temperature about 4 °C and the peak area was increased significantly. However, the higher melting peak around 105-110 °C still exhibited small endothermic peak unaffected by the cooling process, as it only represents the melting of hard-segment crystals.

Previous studies have concluded that the crystallinity of PU is provided by the soft segments. As the hard segments have higher polarity than soft segments, they interact with each other faster than the soft segments, and thus, the part of the PU structure due to the hard segments would be less crystalline than the one due to the soft segments, which are able to reorganize themselves until they reach a more stable disposition before interacting with each other, and hence, give a structure with maximum crystallinity [14].

The CTO-U/Talc-SA-2wt%, CTO-U/MWNT1200-2wt%, MCO-U/Talc-SA-2wt% and MCO-U/MWNT1200-2wt% nanocomposites showed the almost same melting behaviour as pristine ECO-U. As shown in Fig. 13, their lower-melting peak appeared in the first-scan DSC thermogram and second-scan endothermic peak moved to a higher temperature region. In this case, the heterogeneous nucleation effect would gradually evolve, providing more sites for nucleation and accelerating the deposition of polymer molecules [15]. Moreover, the peak area is significantly increased by the addition of Talc-SA and MWNT1200. There are two major effects acting simultaneously when the inorganic particles filled polymer undergoes crystallization. One is the heterogeneous nucleation and the other is decrease in mobility of the chain segments. The heterogeneous nucleation would accelerate the deposition of polymer molecules and in turn increase T_c . However, lowering in molecular mobility would play a reverse effect on the perfect crystallite and in turn lower T_c [15]. Considering that a lower melting enthalpy of BIO-U can be associated to a lower

degree of phase separation, the lower crystallinity can be related to a smaller degree of phase separation.

3.5 Thermal stability of nanocomposites

The thermal stability of the pristine BIO-U and their nanocomposites was studied by TG with under nitrogen atmosphere. From Fig. 14, TG curves for decomposition of all samples showed two-stage decomposition and an initial weight loss in the range of 210-310 °C, suggesting that degradation starts at the urethane bond. The thermal degradation of PU usually initiates from the urethane bonds of hard segment, followed by oxidation of the soft segment phase. In general, the thermal degradation of PU occurs in two stages: the initial degradation stage I is primarily the decomposition of the hard segment, which involves the dissociation of urethane into the original polyol and isocyanate, which then forms a primary amine, alkene and carbon dioxide. This stage is influenced by the hard segment content. The consequent stage II proceeds by the depolycondensation and polyol degradation mechanisms, and is affected by the soft segment content [16].

The decomposition temperature for PTMG based PU is at about 286 °C, but for BIO-U, the initial decomposition temperature is greater than 300 °C. It can be seen that the thermal behaviour of the three samples was identical up to 300 °C and the weight loss was within 5 %. It can be also found that the initial degradation temperature is shifted to lower temperature with increasing the OH-functionality. The initial degradation temperature was in the order of PU-PTMG < MTO-U < CTO-U < ECO-U.

The mass of final residue was also different. For the PU-PTMG sample, the degradation finished at 462 °C, the final residue was 2.4 %. For ECO-U, the degradation finished at 502 °C, the final residue was 4.3 %. This enhanced thermal stability was most likely due to form a cross-linked network structure.

When 2 wt% of the Talc-SA and MWNT1200 were added into ECO-U, the TG traces show a significant shift of the weight loss towards higher temperature than the neat polymer. Because of their high thermal stability; inorganic filler particles act as the thermal insulator. For polymer/silicate nanocomposites, the incorporation of clay into the polymer matrix is generally found to enhance thermal stability by acting as a superior insulator and mass transport

barrier to the volatile products generated during decomposition, as well as by assisting in the formation of char after thermal decomposition [17, 18]. Another possible contributing factor to this improved thermal stability is likely associated with the interaction between polymer and nanofiller. An interaction between the filler and the polymer molecules may thus create an interfacial zone of polymer with reduced mobility. This reduced mobility material in turn causes an increase in the thermal properties of the composite.

3.6 Mechanical properties of nanocomposites

The effect of the incorporating surface-treated Talc and MWNT on the mechanical properties of BIO-U was investigated by tensile test. Tensile properties of dumbbell specimens were determined with a universal test machine (UTM) at a cross-head speed of 500 mm/min in accordance with IEC 60811-1-1 specification.

Fig. 15 shows a stress-strain curve for prepared nanocomposites. The CTO-U, ECO-U and MCO-U showed a tensile behavior represents predominantly an elastic material. The ultimate elongation was over 1000 % and a large degree of strain recovery was observed. The tensile strength at break of CTO-U, ECO-U and MCO-U was 23.8, 26.2 and 24.0 MPa, respectively.

It is to be noted that the tensile strength for ECO-U and Talc nanocomposite was higher compared to other two combinations. The addition of 2 wt% Talc increased tensile strength by 19.8 % when compared with neat ECO. For ECO/MWNT nanocomposite, the addition of 2 wt% MWNT increased tensile strength by 9.1 % when compared to ECO. The ECO/MWNT-2wt% nanocomposite has lower values of both tensile strength and elongation at break in comparison with the ECO/Talc-2wt% one, as a consequence of weaker adhesion.

It can be also found that the surface-treated Talc and MWNT nanocomposites developed higher tensile strength than untreated ones. The reinforcement effect is more pronounced for ECO-U/Talc-SA-2wt% nanocomposite. An approximately 34.4 % overall increase in the tensile strength of 40.6 MPa was observed pre-treatment of the Talc with SA (30.2 MPa). In addition, significant increased tensile strength and elongation at break were obtained for CTO-U/Talc-SA-2wt%, MCO-U/Talc-SA-2wt% and MCO-U/MWNT1200-2wt% nanocomposites.

In general, elongation at break of composite materials decreased with the presence of filler that indicates interference by the filler in the mobility or deformability of the matrix. An increase in weight percentage of filler reduced the deformability of the matrix, and, in turn, reducing the ductility in the skin area so that the composite tended to form a weak structure [19].

This improvement in elongation at break can be explained as the consequence of better stress transfer through the composite due to an improved adhesion between matrix polymer and surface-treated filler. It is clear that surface treatment of nanofiller improve the interface adhesion between polymer matrix and filler particles. The result is filler-polymer bonding that increases tensile strength and improves other compound properties [20-21].

4 Conclusions

The preparation of biopolymers from renewable resources is significant economic and scientific importance. Some studies were carried out to investigate the preparation and properties of castor oil based BIO-U nanocomposites produced by in-situ polymerization method. Increased tensile strength and elongation at break were obtained for MCO-U/Talc-SA-2wt% and MCO-U/MWNT 1200-2wt% nanocomposites. This can be explained as the consequence of better stress transfer through the composite due to an improved adhesion between matrix and filler particles. Moreover, the thermal stability is significantly enhanced in the presence of Talc-SA and MWNT1200 compared to pure BIO-U. Because of its high thermal stability, inorganic filler particles act as the thermal insulator.

Current interest in nanocomposites has been generated and maintained because inorganic nanofiller filled polymers exhibit unique combinations of properties not achievable with traditional composites. The PU was easily processed using conventional techniques such as extrusion, compression molding, and solvent casting, offering the advantage of easy fabrication into a variety of devices and prostheses. Since the nanocomposites prepared by this method have good thermal and mechanical properties, they can be used for widespread application in a number of technological areas and a range of commodity products, such as polymers for automotive parts, furnishings, construction, and in adhesive and coatings.

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Table 1. Composition of synthesized of BIO-U.

Sample	Prepolymer	Chain extender
CTO-U	PDI/PTMG (2.2:1)	Castor oil
ECO-U	PDI/PTMG (2.2:1)	Epoxidized castor oil
MCO-U	PDI/PTMG (2.2:1)	Methoxylated castor oil
PU-PTMG	PDI/PTMG (2.2:1)	PTMG

Fig. 1. ¹H-NMR spectra of the (a) castor oil (b) epoxidized castor oil and (c) methoxylated castor oil.

Fig. 2. FTIR spectra of the (a) castor oil (b) epoxidized castor oil and (c) methoxylated castor oil.

Fig. 3. FTIR spectra of the (a) Talc and (b) Talc-SA and TEPI-SA.

Fig. 4. FTIR spectra of the (a) pristine MWNT and (b) MWNT1200.

Fig. 5. SEM image of the (a) Talc and (b) Talc-SA.

Fig. 6. SEM image of the (a) pristine MWNT and (b) MWNT-EB.

Fig. 7. FTIR spectra of the synthesized (a) CTO-U, (b) ECO-U (c) MCO-U and (d) PU-PTMG.

Fig. 8. FTIR spectra of the (a) CTO-U, (b) ECO-U, (c) MCO-U and (d) PU-PTMG.

Fig. 9. Fracture surface of (a) CTO-U, (b) ECO-U and (c) MCO-U.

Fig. 10. Fracture surface of (a) CTO-U/MWNT-2wt% and (b) CTO-U/MWNT1200-2wt%.

Fig. 11. Fracture surface of the (a) MCO-U/Talc-2wt% and (b) MCO-U/Talc-SA-2wt%.

Fig. 12. DSC thermograms of the (a) CTO-U, (b) ECO-U, (c) MCO-U and (d) PU-PTMG [First- (....) and second-scan (—)].

Fig. 13. First (....) and second-scan (—) DSC thermograms of the nanocomposites.

Fig. 14. TG traces of the synthesized BIO-U and their nanocomposites.

Fig. 15. Stress-strain curve of the prepared nanocomposites have taken from the middle value of the tensile data set.